

Motivation of Job Seekers to be Civil Servants

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Abstract. The large number of companies established in Batam city resulted to the opening of the many jobs. But the large number of private companies erected in Batam is not making job seekers to lose their interest to register themselves into the civil service. In 2014 there are 3.873 people who apply to be civil servants for 94 formations. The purpose of this research is to investigate the main motivation of job-seeker on Batam to become civil officer, based on gender restriction and family factor. Sample used in this research are 268 university students that have been studied public sector accounting on Batam. To determine the results, writer used qualitative research method with questionnaire. Gathered data are analyzed with confirmatory factor analysis. Stabilized future and secure environment are the main factor for the job-seeker on Batam to become civil officer, based on gender restriction and family factor. This study intended specifically to the staffing Agency of Batam to be material consideration in hiring. This research is limited to students who have studied public sector accounting in batam, then the author suggested to expand the sample in the future research.

Keywords: motivation, spirit of serving the public, social status, work security, gender, family factor

Introduction

Since January 19, 2009 Batam officially applied free trade zone. About 5.608 listed companies stand in Batam consisting of agriculture, forestry, fisheries, mining, electricity, gas, water construction, trade, hotel, transportation, storage and communications, finance, insurance, and services (BPS, 2014). The number of companies established in Batam affect on jobs opening. The number of private companies in Batam do not make the interest of job seekers declined to register themselves into a civil servant. This thing evidenced in 2014 there were 3.873 people who apply to become a civil servant in Batam (Ferri, 2014).

Based on the announcement Number 1273/BKD-PK/X/2014 on the results of the administration selection of civil servant candidates in the areas out of general applicants around Batam government in 2014 there were 3.351 people who have passed the administrative selection. Participants who have passed the administration will undergo further tests for 94 formations provided this is accordance to the

announcement Number 110/BKD-TU/IX/2014 on recruitment of civil servants candidate in the city government of Batam formation in 2014 needed 94 people to be admitted to be the civil servants. This will create a significant comparative between 3.873 registrants and 94 formations required is 1:36. Looking at the significant comparisons between the job seekers in the private sector and the Civil Servants would cause a phenomenon, although the opportunity to become a civil servants is hard, but the job seekers is enthusiastic to register themselves as civil servants (Perry & Wise, 1990).

The problems of this study were 1) what is the main factor that motivate prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil servants, 2) what is the main factor that motivate prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil servants in terms of gender, and 3) what is the main factor that motivate prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil servants in terms of family factors.

Motivation variable is limited only to discuss the motivation of the prospective job seekers in Batam to

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become civil servants in Batam, using a rating scale to see the most important motivation. The motivation was adopted from Ko & Han (2013) which consists of a future stable and secure, the opportunity to learn new things, the opportunity to give benefit to the society, the opportunity to learn the leadership, working as a team, variations in employment, high prestige and social status, place of work that friendly and pleasant, high salary, the opportunity to use the special abilities, the opportunity to join to set up the important decisions, freedom from supervision, the opportunity to engage in recreational activities, freedom from the pressure to adapt both within and off the job, and career opportunities.

Literature Review

Motivation

Motivation is more focused on how to steer the power and potential in work to achieve the goals set (Hasibuan, 2014). According to Robbins (2001), motivation is a process that measure the intensity, direction and persistence in achieving goals. The motivation of each individual is different and causing the tendency of diversity in the selection of work. According to Purwanto (2006) motivation refers to a process that affects a person's choice of the various forms of activity which they are desired. Purwanto (2006) also explain the motivation contains three main components, which are moving, directs and sustains behavior.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Fig 1. Hierarchy of Needs

(Wijayanto, 2012)

Hierarchy of needs theory developed by Abraham Maslow consider some need to explain human behavior (Pareek, 1984). The human need according to Maslow has a level or hierarchy. If the basic human needs tend to not pay attention to other needs that has

higher level after they fulfill the physiological needs (Wijayanto, 2012).

Public Service Motivation

Theory of public service motivation or commonly referred as PSM describes the tendency of an individual to respond to the basic motives are unique in institutions and public organizations. PSM can also encourage people to do something good to others and donate their devotion to welfare organizations and society. There are three motives characterized in PSM such as rational motive, norms and affective (Perry and Wise, 1990).

Social status is a set of rights and obligations that person has in society. According to Porlak (1979), which referred to social status is a social status in society. People who have a higher social status in the structure of society then they will be placed higher than the person who has a low social status (Linton, 2010).

Job security can not be separated from the attention to the uncertainty of someone's job and the continuation of the uncertain situation due to changes in the organization. Variable job security includes three-dimensional such as future careers, promotion and job security in general (Davy et al., 1997).

Etymologically the word "gender" is derived from the English, which means sex (Echols & Shadilly, 1983). The term gender is used to describe the differences between women and men are innate as a divine creation. In general, gender has spawned the different roles, responsibilities, functions, and even space where human do activity (Puspitawati, 2013). According to Robbins (2008) there is no much difference between the performance of men and women. For example there were no differences related to the ability to solve problems, analyze, competitive urge, motivation and learning.

Family is defined as a group of people who live in one house and still have a kinship, blood ties, birth and adoption (Soekanto, 2004). Here is the main function of the family according to Khairuddin (1997) which is a Biological function, affection, and Socialization.

Research Design

Characteristic of Respondents

Respondents in this study were university students in Batam who has studied Public Sector Accounting.

Out of the 350 questionnaires distributed, 268 questionnaires were returned and processed. Samples can be taken is shown in the following table.

Table 1 Characteristic of Respondents

Description	Total
Questioner distributed	350
Questioner feedback from respondents	268
No feedback from respondents	82
Total	268

Table 2. Characteristic Respondents Based on Sex

Sex	Total (Pax)	Percent
Male	50	18,7%
Female	218	81,3%
Total	268	100,0%

Table 3 Characteristic Respondents Based on Varian Job

Job	Total (Pax)	Percent
Civil servants	148	55,2%
State-owned enterprises	23	8,6%
Private companies	65	24,3%
Others	32	11,9%
Total	268	100,0%

Results and Discussion

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

The following Table 4 is a CFA test results to determine the motivation of the prospective job seekers in Batam to become a civil servant:

Table 4 Indicator of Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

Variable	K	R	SD	U
A stable and secure future	Q1	2.72	3.192	1
Chance to learn new things	Q2	5.14	3.417	2
Chance to benefit society	Q3	5.48	3.939	3
Chance to exercise leadership	Q4	5.86	3.362	4
Chance of career	Q15	7.70	4.128	5
Working as part of a team	Q5	7.70	3.585	6
Chance to use a special abilities	Q10	7.90	2.991	7
High salary	Q9	8.49	4.511	8
Freedom from pressures to conform both on and off the job	Q14	8.61	3.547	9
Good workplace and friendly	Q8	8.82	4.236	10
Variety in work assignments	Q6	9.23	3.008	11
Chance to make a contribution to important decisions	Q11	10.43	3.247	12
Freedom from supervision	Q12	10.53	3.722	13
High prestige and social status	Q7	10.58	4.122	14
Chance to engage in satisfying leisure activities	Q13	10.95	3.953	15

Based on Table 4 the future that stable and secure is the primary motivation that make prospective job

seekers in Batam to become civil servants. The last motivation for prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil servants is an opportunity to engage in recreational activities.

Motivation Male Candidate Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

The following table 5 is a CFA test results to determine the motivation of the prospective male job seekers in Batam to become a civil servant:

Table 5 Indicator of Motivation Male Candidate Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

Variable	K	R	SD	U
A stable and secure future	Q1	4.70	4.802	1
Chance to exercise leadership	Q4	5.10	3.144	2
Chance to benefit society	Q3	5.55	5.094	3
Chance to learn new things	Q2	5.70	4.244	4
Working as part of a team	Q5	6.25	2.751	5
Chance of career	Q15	7.10	3.796	6
Chance to use a special abilities	Q10	7.70	3.114	7
Variety in work assignments	Q6	7.90	2.827	8
Chance to make a contribution to important decisions	Q11	9.30	3.466	9
High salary	Q9	9.30	3.358	10
Good workplace and friendly	Q8	9.30	2.515	11
Freedom from pressures to conform both on and off the job	Q14	9.45	4.298	12
High prestige and social status	Q7	9.85	4.848	13
Freedom from supervision	Q12	10.90	4.352	14
Chance to engage in satisfying leisure activities	Q13	11.90	3.905	15

Based on Table 5 the future that stable and secure is the main motivation that make male job seekers in Batam to become civil servants in Batam. The last motivates prospective male job seekers in Batam to become civil servants is an opportunity to engage in recreational activities.

Motivation Female Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

The following Table 6 is a CFA test results to determine the motivation of the prospective female job seekers in Batam to become civil servants:

Table 6 Indicator of Motivation Female Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

Variable	K	R	SD	U
A stable and secure future	Q1	2.41	2.762	1
Chance to learn new things	Q2	5.05	3.280	2
Chance to benefit society	Q3	5.47	3.752	3
Chance to exercise leadership	Q4	5.98	3.391	4
Chance of career	Q15	7.79	4.184	5
Working as part of a team	Q5	7.92	3.656	6

Chance to use a special abilities	Q10	7.93	2.983	7
High salary	Q9	8.36	4.663	8
Freedom from pressures to conform both on and off the job	Q14	8.48	3.416	9
Good workplace and friendly	Q8	8.74	4.448	10
Variety in work assignments	Q6	9.44	2.993	11
Freedom from supervision	Q12	10.48	3.631	12
Chance to make a contribution to important decisions	Q11	10.60	3.190	13
High prestige and social status	Q7	10.70	4.007	14
Chance to engage in satisfying leisure activities	Q13	10.80	3.955	15

Based on Table 6 the opportunity to engage in recreational activities is the last sequence that motivation female job seekers candidates in Batam to become civil servants. The future that stable and secure is the primary motivation who make female job-seeker in Batam to become civil servants in Batam.

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam who came from Civil Servant's family to become a Civil Servant

The following Table 7 is the CFA test results to determine the motivation of the prospective job seekers who came from civil servant's family in Batam to become a civil servant:

Table 7

Indicator of Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam who came from Civil Servant's family to become a Civil Servant

Variable	K	R	SD	U
A stable and secure future	Q1	2.88	3.347	1
Chance to learn new things	Q2	4.99	3.223	2
Chance to exercise leadership	Q4	5.36	3.202	3
Chance to benefit society	Q3	5.55	4.096	4
Working as part of a team	Q5	7.75	3.786	5
Chance to use a special abilities	Q10	7.78	3.150	6
Chance of career	Q15	8.22	4.468	7
Variety in work assignments	Q6	8.69	2.769	8
Freedom from pressures to conform both on and off the job	Q14	8.75	3.400	9
High salary	Q9	9.34	4.686	10
Good workplace and friendly	Q8	9.34	3.866	11
High prestige and social status	Q7	10.03	3.873	12
Freedom from supervision	Q12	10.17	3.909	13
Chance to engage in satisfying leisure activities	Q13	10.36	4.173	14
Chance to make a contribution to important decisions	Q11	10.99	3.181	15

Based on Table 7 future that stable and secure is the primary motivation that make job-seeker who comes from a family of civil servants in Batam to become a civil servants. The last sequence motivate that make job-seeker who comes from a family of civil servants

in Batam to become civil servants is an opportunity to join in establishing an important decision.

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam is Not Derived from Civil Servant's Family to Become a Civil Servant

The following Table 8 is a CFA test results to determine the motivation of the prospective job seekers who do not come from a family of civil servants in Batam to become a civil servant:

Table 8

Indicator of Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam is Not Derived from Civil Servant's Family to Become a Civil Servant

Variable	K	R	SD	U
A stable and secure future	Q1	2.37	2.877	1
Chance to learn new things	Q2	5.33	3.735	2
Chance to benefit society	Q3	5.37	3.646	3
Chance of career	Q15	6.71	3.244	4
Working as part of a team	Q4	6.73	3.487	5
High salary	Q9	6.88	3.682	6
Chance to exercise leadership	Q5	7.67	3.123	7
Good workplace and friendly	Q8	7.83	4.714	8
Chance to use a special abilities	Q10	8.10	2.724	9
Freedom from pressures to conform both on and off the job	Q14	8.29	3.806	10
Chance to make a contribution to important decisions	Q11	9.37	3.106	11
Variety in work assignments	Q6	10.21	3.201	12
Freedom from supervision	Q12	11.38	3.069	13
High prestige and social status	Q7	11.75	4.383	14
Chance to engage in satisfying leisure activities	Q13	12.02	3.281	15

Based on Table 8 the opportunity to engage in recreational activities is the last sequence that make motivation of job-seeker who does not come from civil servant's family in Batam to become civil servants. The future that stable and secure is the primary motivation who make job-seeker who does not come from civil servant's family in Batam to become civil servants in Batam.

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

The future that stable and secure with regard to job security, defined as someone's expectations to the continuity of their work. Job security by Davy et al., (1997) includes a future career, promotional opportunities, and job security in general. Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 5 of 2014 on the Reform of Civil State Chapter VI Rights and Obligations section to the article 21 of the civil servants entitled to receive: 1) salary, benefits, and facilities, 2) leave, 3) pension and old age security, 4)

protection, and 5) development competencies, this led to a job as a civil servant that guarantees job security.

Civil servants have multiple functions and service units that require different skills in each unit, it certainly can make prospective job seekers can learn something new if they become a civil servant. Worked as a civil servant must have a public service orientation. Public service motivation can encourage people to do good things to others and donate their devotion to welfare organizations and society (Perry & Wise, 1990). Working as civil servants must provide good career opportunities for prospective job seekers in Batam. Position available as a civil servant can be obtained or increased accordance with the rank held by the educational background and training that has been through.

Motivation Male Candidate Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

Male is head of a household that has a primary obligation to make a living (Sukidin, 2000). The rise of the issue of layoffs that a lot of companies did would lead to stability and security in work as top priority for choosing a job. Loso (2008) argues that life as a civil servant is more promising than other professions such as private life with layoffs.

Motivation Female Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to Become Civil Servants

A woman must have natures after marriage then they will pregnant and give birth. Companies often making it as a base to force workers to resign or termination of employment (PHK) (Permatawi & Purwanti, 2012). The government through legislation and government regulations provide opportunities for female civil servants to get maternity leave without losing her job as a civil servant.

According to Sukidin (2000), women have limitations as an individual in terms of access to education, experience and work skills. These limitations make female prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil servants to be more motivated to learn new things not exercise leadership.

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam to become Civil Servants Viewed from Family Factor

If someone who worked as civil servants were satisfied with their jobs then they would recommend their children or their family members to work as a

civil servant (Ko & Han, 2013). Of course, the satisfaction of a civil servant based by a sense of security and a stable future with their work. It make students who come from a family of civil servants motivated by the future that stable and secure to become civil servants.

Motivation Candidates Job Seekers in Batam Were Not Derived from Civil Servant's Family to Become a Civil Servant

Loso (2008) suggests that heredity ranks quite low position in relation to the causes of job-seeker become civil servants. The same motivation is caused by the paradigm of society that works as a civil servant is a job that guarantees life and have a good level of security if the terms of layoffs.

Conclusion

This study shows that job seekers in Batam motivated to become a civil servant because of the future stable and secure. In terms of gender there were no differences in the primary motivation that caused male prospective job seekers female to become civil servants. The future that stable and secure is the motivation of the male and female prospective job seekers to become civil servants in Batam. Family factors in terms of the main motivations that motivate potential job seekers to become civil servants in Batam also made no distinction of motivation to become civil servants. The future that stable and secure motivate job-seeker who comes from a family of civil servants and that does not come from a family of civil servants in Batam to become civil servants.

There are several limitations in this study. First, this study only examined students from five universities accredited by BAN-PT in Batam, they are State Polytechnic of Batam, Riau Kepulauan University, Putera Batam University and Batam International University. Second, the scope of the research is limited only for students who have studied public sector accounting, the majority of respondents who have studied these courses have a final semester and is in the process of apprenticeship making it difficult to distribute questionnaires.

The implication of this research is aimed for researchers, job seekers, as well as local civil body of Batam as a form of consideration as well as information relating to the motivation of the prospective job seekers in Batam to become civil

servants. This research study is expected to provide a reference for further research to develop this research. Suggestions of Researchers should be in a set of samples for future studies and more expanded.

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